

long. Two 6-cm-diameter petri dishes washed with a layer of moist cotton overlaid with a circular piece of black cotton cloth are fitted onto each end of the wire gauze cylinder with rubber bands (see figure).

Two pairs of moths can be released inside the cage through a hole made in the wire gauze. The hole is closed with a ball of cotton dipped in 25% honey solution.

We kept cages with moths in darkness. Eggs were laid on the black cloth. They were removed daily and the black cloth reused.

The number of eggs laid on cloth and on potted rice plants did not differ (see table). However, when cellulose paper was substituted for black cloth, no eggs were laid.

Hatchability of eggs laid on cloth was >90%. Also, freshly laid eggs are easily counted against the dark background. (No color preference by the

Cage for oviposition of rice LF.

moths is implied.) Eggs collected on a nonplant substrate, such as cloth, are easier to sterilize.

Collecting eggs on cloth would be useful in large-scale rearing of LF and when first-instar larvae are to be infested with minimum handling. This method would be particularly useful where larvae are to be tested in sterile conditions, such as on callus and on artificial diets. The oviposition cage can also be used in assaying various LF

Oviposition of the rice LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée) on rice leaves and nonplant substrates.

Substrate	Eggs/2 females per d (mean ± SE)
On potted IR36 plants in the insectary	56 ± 15
On black cloth in the oviposition cages	63 ± 9

^aAv of 9 replications.

attractants and oviposition stimulants. □

A nuclear polyhedrosis virus from rice skipper

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Rice skipper *Pelopidas mathias* (Fabricius) occurs mostly in rainfed rice. It causes damage similar to that from other rice defoliators (armyworms and rice green semiloopers).

We isolated a nuclear polyhedrosis virus (PmNPV) from a rice skipper colony in the greenhouse at IRRI. Virus-infected rice skippers were sluggish, ceased feeding, and died. Cadavers exhibited typical symptoms of virus-killed larvae: black color and liquefied body contents.

We purified the PmNPV by macerating PmNPV-infected rice skipper larvae with 0.1% sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) in a glass homogenizer and filtering through four layers of

cheesecloth to remove large particles of insect debris. The filtrate was centrifuged at 100 g (1,000 rpm in Beckman rotor JA-20) for 1 min and the precipitate was discarded.

The supernatant was centrifuged at 2,500 g (6,000 rpm in Beckman rotor JA-20) for 10 min to remove lipid, soluble material, and small contaminants. The pellet was resuspended with 0.1% SDS and the centrifuging cycle repeated three times.

The final pellet was resuspended in a small volume of distilled water and centrifuged on 30-80% (vol/vol) discontinuous glycerol gradients in a Beckman SW-27 swing bucket rotor with a Beckman L8-M ultracentrifuge at 1,500 g or 3,500 rpm for 10 min.

The white virus band was collected, diluted with distilled water, and centrifuged at 2,500 g for 10 min. The supernatant was discarded and the pellet resuspended in distilled water and centrifuged on 25-60% (wt/wt) linear sucrose gradients in a Beckman SW-27 rotor at 1,500 g or 10,000 rpm for 30 min.

The virus band formed was collected

with a pipette, diluted with distilled water, and centrifuged at 2,500 g for 30 min to remove the sucrose. The pellet was suspended in distilled water and stored in a freezer.

The 0.858 ± 0.143 μm polyhedra was somewhat tetragonal (Fig. 1).

The virions in the polyhedra were released by mixing equal volume of PmNPV suspension with 0.1 M NaCO₃ (pH = 10.7) for 60 min at 30 °C. The

1. Electron micrograph of the nuclear polyhedrosis virus from the rice skipper *Pelopidas mathias* stained with 2% PTA.

released virions were stained with 2% phosphotungstic acid (PTA) and examined under electron microscope. The rod-shaped virions (Fig. 2) were 367.84 ± 26.85 nm long and 64.37 ± 5.63 nm wide.

This is the first known evidence of a nuclear polyhedrosis virus from *P. mathias* in the Philippines. □

2. Virions released from the polyhedra after 1-h treatment with 0.05 M NaCO₃ at 30°C. A) Virions in the polyhedral membrane; B) virions released from polyhedra.

Simulation of rice yield reduction caused by stem borer (SB)

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We adapted a rice crop growth model to simulate yield reduction caused by SB on irrigated IR64 at IRRI. Grain yield predicted by the model correlated well with yield obtained by clipping tillers in the field.

The computer simulations predicted that up to 20% deadhearts at the

vegetative stage would cause no significant reduction in grain yield— young plants could compensate for lost tillers. Damage at the grain filling stage (whiteheads) caused an almost proportionate yield reduction (see figure).

This suggests that spraying against SB at the early vegetative stage is often unnecessary, since young rice plants can tolerate considerable damage.

The computer simulations also suggest that yield reduction caused by SB is larger at low N levels since compensation then is less effective. Such physical factors as low radiation also can aggravate SB damage.

Simulated grain yield of IR64 in response to damage inflicted at 4 crop stages—active tillering (23 d after transplanting [DT]), maximum tillering (33 DT), panicle initiation (43 DT), and flowering (69 DT)—by clipping a fraction of tillers in each hill. Full lines (—) represent response when tillers are removed, dotted lines (· · ·) represent response when killed tillers are kept in place (natural stem borer damage). The difference is due to shading.

Life history of water strider *Limnogonus fossarum* (F.)

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L. fossarum is a common predator in wetland ricefields in the Philippines. An adult female water strider can consume up to 20 BPH a day.

We collected 100 eggs laid on cut TN1 rice stems. Emerging nymphs

Clipping tillers is an artificial method for mimicking deadhearts or whiteheads. It is relatively easy to carry out, but, unlike with natural SB damage, tillers removed by clipping no longer provide shade. We also used the model to compute how much results of experiments using the clipping method need to be adjusted to agree with natural SB damage (see figure).

Using the same model, similar field experiments and simulations were conducted at several research institutes under various weather conditions and using different varieties. Results confirmed that the model is not location specific. □

were released separately in 9-cm-diam petri dishes filled with distilled water and enclosed in 14-cm-high mylar cages with nylon mesh tops. Each cage contained cut TN1 stems and BPH for food. The cages were kept at 25–30 °C, 70–90% RH, and 12/24 h illumination.

As adults emerged, they were paired and kept inside 0.5-gal containers for oviposition. Survival and female fecundity were recorded daily.

Life cycle of the water strider was